

Modelling and strategies for the assessment and **Optimisation**
of **Energy Usage** aspects of rail innovation

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AC – Alternating Current

DC – Direct Current

ESS – Energy Storage System

E-transformer – Electrical Transformer

HVAC – Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning

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WP – Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The work presented in this deliverable D05.1 has been carried out in the framework of the collaboration agreement between OPEUS and the Shift2Rail Members project FINE1 (Grant agreement No. 730818). The present work is also in close relation with the work carried out in WP02, where OPEUS simulation tool has been developed.

This document presents a description of the traction system and auxiliaries parameter based on the vehicle architecture. The general defined vehicle architecture depends on the catenary voltage system, from which the specific architecture for each scenario (urban, regional, high-speed and freight) can be elaborated. A specific conventional tram architecture is presented as example, where all traction components (converters, traction motors, etc.) are also defined and described. At the end of the report there is a proposal of some topologies as well as some energy and management strategies in order to run simulations and to investigate possible measures for reduction of energy losses in task 5.2 of OPEUS project.

1 INTRODUCTION

WP05 “In-vehicle energy losses study” of OPEUS project aims at investigating the energy losses within the traction chain, using the duty cycles defined in previous projects (CleanER-D and Roll2Rail projects) and the urban duty cycles defined in collaboration between OPEUS and FINE1 partners.

This Deliverable D05.1 presents the work carried out in the first task of WP05, “Task5.1 - Vehicle architecture characterisation”, which describes the traction system and auxiliary parameter based on the vehicle architecture related to the different scenarios. The work has been done in collaboration with FINE1 partners.

The report is divided in different chapters that describe the different activities done:

- General vehicle architectures are presented in chapter 2 for electric train vehicles. Its definition depends on the catenary voltage system.
- Out of the defined general topologies, the specific architecture for each scenario (urban, regional, high-speed and freight) can be done by selecting the right components. A specific conventional tram architecture is presented as example in chapter 3, where all traction components (converters, traction motors, etc.) are also defined and described.
- Finally, some topologies are selected and the management of the auxiliary systems is defined in chapter 4 in order to run the simulations and to investigate possible measures for reduction of energy losses in task 5.2.

2 DEFINITION OF VEHICLE TOPOLOGIES

This chapter describes the propulsion system topologies to be considered in OPEUS tool for simulation.

Three common topologies/architectures for electric train vehicles have been defined according to the catenary voltage system. The component arrangement for each topology has been defined in a general way, which means that the same topology, e.g. T01 AC supply system, can be valid for high speed, regional or freight service for instance, but adapting the final characteristics or number of individual components for each specific case.

The topologies include dotted lines for alternative component or interface variants, so in the end OPEUS simulation tool will provide the user with the option to choose a specific variant to be simulated.

2.1 Topologies for AC supply trains (T01)

This topology, presented in Figure 1, describes trains supplied by 15kV AC or 25kV AC voltage via overhead catenary and a conventional iron core transformer.

Figure 1: AC topology with conventional transformer (T01)

2.2 Topologies for AC supply trains, with e-transformer (T02)

This topology, shown in Figure 2, describes trains supplied by 15kV AC or 25kV AC voltage and an electronic transformer.

Figure 2: AC topology with e-transformer (T02)

2.3 Topologies for DC supply trains (T03)

This topology, Figure 3, is used for trains supplied by 750V, 1500V or 3000V DC.

Figure 3: DC Topology (T03)

3 SYSTEM COMPONENT CHARACTERISTICS

This chapter refers to the system component and the parameters used inside the above topologies. A detailed description of the model of each component is included in Deliverable "D02.1 - OPEUS simulation methodology".

Within the common working group of OPEUS and FINE1 partners, the components have been labeled with C numbers (as can be seen in Figures 1 to 3 in Chapter 2) and every component is described by several ID parameters, which are implemented in the component model tool.

Table 1 below lists all components used in the topologies defined in Chapter 2.

ID	Name	Description	Comments
C00	Vehicle	Body of the train/ represents the running resistance	Described via the parameters Par000-Par039
C04	Axle Gear Box	Gearing between the wheel hub and the motor shaft/ constant ratio	Described via the parameters Par040-Par049
C05	Induction Motor	Transducer between electrical and mechanical power/ asynchronous operation	Described via the parameters Par050-Par059
C06	Synchronous Motor	Transducer between electrical and mechanical power/ synchronous operation	Described via the parameters Par060-Par069
C07	Motor Converter	Transforms DC to 3phase AC/ standard power semiconductor (e.g. SiO2-IGBT)	Described via the parameters Par070-Par079
C08	Motor Converter - SiC	Transforms DC to 3phase AC/ Silicon-carbide power semiconductors	Described via the parameters Par080-Par089
C09	Rheostat Converter	DC-to-DC converter/ transform DC circuit volt level to rheostat volt level	Described via the parameters Par090-Par099
C10	Rheostat	Braking resistance	Described via the parameters Par100-Par109
C11	DC Intermediate Circuit	Second harmonic filter/ absorption circuit: to filter residual ripple, only in AC power supply	Described via the parameters Par110-Par119
C12	Line Converter	Commutate 1phase AC to DC/ only in AC power supply	Described via the parameters Par120-Par129

C13	Transformer	Transformation between two AC volt levels/ only in AC power supply	Described via the parameters Par130-Par139
C14	E-Transformer	Transforms AC to DC/ combination of standard transformer and power semiconductors/ only in AC power supply	Described via the parameters Par140-Par149
C15	Line Inductor	Line inductor used to optimize current transition / only in DC power supply	Described via the parameters Par150-Par159
C16	ESS Converter	DC-to-DC converter/ transform DC circuit volt level to ESS-battery volt level	Described via the parameters Par160-Par169
C17	ESS Battery (Li-Ion)	Energy storage system for recover braking energy/ Battery as a high energy storage	Described via the parameters Par170-Par189
C19	DLC converter	DC-to-DC converter/ transform DC circuit volt level to DLC volt level	Described via the parameters Par190-Par199
C20	DLC	Energy storage system for recovering braking energy/ DLC as a high power storage	Described via the parameters Par200-Par219
C22	Auxiliary Converter at DC-link	Converts DC to 3phase AC for 3phase AC loads/ 400Vrms@50Hz	Described via the parameters Par220-Par229
C23	Electrical Auxiliary at DC-link	Consumption of electrical auxiliaries which are linked to the DC intermediate circuit/ could differ regarding different seasons	Described via the parameters Par230-Par239
C24	Auxiliary Converter at Transformer	Converts 1phase AC to 3phase AC for 3phase AC loads/ 400Vrms@50Hz	Described via the parameters Par240-Par249
C25	Electrical Auxiliary at Transformer	Consumption of electrical auxiliaries which are linked to a special transformer coil/ could differ regarding different seasons	Described via the parameters Par250-Par259
C26	Battery Converter	DC-to-DC converter/ transform DC circuit volt level to on board battery volt level	Described via the parameters Par260-Par269
C27	Battery Consumption	Battery for on board power supply/ 24Vdc	Described via the parameters Par270-Par279
C30	Infrastructure	Track description, speed limits, time table	Described via the parameters Par300 - Par309

Table 1 Electric Traction System Components

The description of all system component characteristics of the traction system, its interface variables and parameters, as well as a detailed modelling are part of Deliverable D02.1 OPEUS simulation methodology. Annex A of this Deliverable D02.1 contains the mentioned values for every service category.

Depending on the service category and the supply voltage system some components are not needed. For instance, in DC lines, which is very common in tram or metro service, no absorption circuit (C11), line converter (C12) or transformer (C13) are present.

In addition, some components would be part of future research, like C06 synchronous motor, C08 - motor converter (SiC-semiconductors) or C14 - E-transformer.

As an example, the architecture for a conventional tram vehicle (without ESS) is shown in Figure 4, and the related components and the implemented parameters that will be used for simulation in this case are presented in Table 2.

Figure 4: Topology for a conventional Tram

ID	Descriptive Parameter	Description	Unit	Conventional Tram
C00 - vehicle				
Par003	k0	Coefficient for calculation of resistance force	N	130*num_axles
Par004	k1	Coefficient for calculation of resistance force	kg/s	0
Par005	k2	Coefficient for calculation of resistance force	N/kg	0,0064
Par006	k3	Coefficient for calculation of resistance force	1/s	0,000504
Par007	k4	Coefficient for calculation of resistance force	kg/m	8,0849249
Par008	k5	Coefficient for calculation of resistance force	1/m	0
Par009	m_tare	design mass in working order acc. to EN 15663	t	41
Par010	m_rot	rotating masses (% of m_tare)	%	7
Par012	n_pax	number of passengers		200
Par013	m_pax	mass per passenger	kg	75
Par015	v_max	maximum velocity	km/h	70/80
Par016	d_wheel	wheel diameter	mm	600
Par017	v_wind	head wind velocity	km/h	0
Par018	f_tunnel	Increase of aerodynamic resistance within tunnels	%	100
Par030	length	Train length	m	32
C04 - Gearbox				
Par040	i_GB	gear ratio wheelset gearbox		9
Par041	h_GB	efficiency map as a function of torque and wheel speed - $h = f(T, w_{wheel})$		0,98
C05 - Induction motor				
Par050	n_mot	number of motors	integer	4
Par051	P_max	maximum power per motor	kW	100 (nominal)
Par052	η_{mot}	efficiency map as a function of torque and motor speed - $\eta = f(T, w_{mot})$		See map
Par053	P_loss_idle	power losses during no load operation	kW	3
Par054	P_cool	electric power demand for cooling at Aux converter output as a function of the load	kW_el / kW_load	1%
C07 - motor converter (basic-semiconductors)				
Par070	n_mc	number of converters	integer	2
Par071	P_max	maximum power per converter	kW	360(trac) 560(brake)
Par072	η_{mc}	efficiency map as a function of load and motor speed - $\eta = f(P, w_{mot})$		See map
Par073	P_loss_idle	power losses during no load operation	kW	10
Par074	P_cool	cooling power as a function of the load	kW	2.5%
C09 - rheostat converter				
Par090	n_rc	number of converters	integer	2
Par091	P_max	maximum power per converter	kW	560
Par092	η_{rc}	efficiency map as a function of load - $\eta = f(P)$		See map

Par093	P_loss_idle	power losses during no load operation	kW	0
Par094	P_cool	electric power demand for cooling at Aux converter output as a function of the load	kW_el / kW_load	0
C10 - rheostat				
Par100	n_rs	number of rheostats	integer	2
Par101	P_max	maximum power per rheostat	kW	560
C15 - Line inductor				
Par150	n_li	number of line inductors	integer	2
Par151	P_max	maximum power per line inductors	kW	1000
Par152	η_{li}	efficiency map as a function of load - $\eta = f(P)$		See map
Par153	P_loss_idle	power losses during no load operation	kW	0
Par154	P_cool	electric power demand for cooling at Aux converter output as a function of the load	kW_el / kW_load	0
C22 - auxiliary converter - connected to DC link				
Par220	n_auxDCc	number of aux. converters	integer	2
Par221	P_max	maximum power per aux. converters	kW	35
Par222	η_{auxDCc}	efficiency map as a function of power and motor speed: $\eta = f(P,w)$		See map
Par223	P_loss_idle	power losses during no load operation	kW	1
Par224	P_cool	electric power demand for cooling at Aux converter output as a function of the load	kW_el / kW_load	2
C23 - electrical auxiliary - DC link				
Par230	P_aux(t) summer	Auxiliary power as a function of time - summer season	kW	82
Par231	P_aux(t) spring/autumn	Auxiliary power as a function of time - winter season	kW	71
Par232	P_aux(t) winter	Auxiliary power as a function of time - spring/autumn season	kW	67
C26 - Battery converter				
Par260	n_batc	number of aux. converters	integer	2
Par261	P_max	maximum power per converter	kW	8
Par262	η_{bat}	efficiency map as a function of power $\eta = f(P)$		0,96
Par263	P_loss_idle	power losses during no load operation	kW	0
Par264	P_cool	electric power demand for cooling at Aux converter output as a function of the load	kW_el / kW_load	0
C27 - Battery consumption				
Par270	P_bat(t)	battery consumption as a function of time	kW	12,5

Table 2: List of components and value parameters in a conventional Tram

As defined in Table 2 above (by C23 - electrical auxiliary - DC link), the electrical auxiliaries may vary depending on the season. In a tram, the biggest influence will come from the HVAC. Of course, the values for auxiliary consumption on each season will depend on the train service and on the area it is operating. The auxiliary values for every service category used for the simulation in OPEUS are included in Annex A of Deliverable 02.1 OPEUS simulation methodology.

4 SELECTION OF TOPOLOGIES AND AUXILIARY SCENARIOS TO BE SIMULATED

4.1 Topologies selection

From topologies and components described in chapter 2 and 3 many potential configurations are possible for the different service categories and duty cycles. OPEUS tool will allow to create and simulate a variety of topologies by rearranging/exchanging the component blocks. However, in order to make comparisons, the baseline simulations will be done with fixed topologies and fixed component characteristics.

Within working group from FINE1 and OPEUS partners, the most current usual topologies for each service category were identified and are presented in Table 3 below.

Service Category	Duty Cycle	Selected Topology	Comments
High Speed	High Speed 300	T01 AC	Common topologies for this service category and duty cycles in EU are AC-25kV/50Hz and AC-15kV/16.7Hz energy supply.
	High Speed 250	T01 AC	
	Intercity	T01 AC	
Regional	Regional 160	T01 AC	Common topologies for this service category and duty cycles in EU are AC-25kV/50Hz and AC-15kV/16.7Hz. However also 1.5kVdc and 3kVdc energy supply are possible.
	Regional 140	T01 AC	
Urban	Tram	T03 DC	Common topology for a tram is to have 750Vdc energy supply
	Metro	T03 DC	Common topology for a metro is to have 1.500Vdc energy supply
	Suburban	T01 AC	Common topology for suburban is AC-25kV/50Hz and AC-15kV/16.7Hz energy supply
Freight	Mainline	T01 AC	Common topologies for this service category and duty cycles in EU are AC-25kV/50Hz and AC-15kV/16.7Hz energy supply. 3KVdc is also possible
	Shunting	Diesel	This was already covered in CleanER-D project. OPEUS tool will include this architecture too.

Table 3: Selected topology according to service category and vehicle type

Note: T02 AC topology may also be simulated, within WP3, in order to check innovations with E-transformers in Shift2Rail.

This pre-selection of architectures and duty cycles to be used for the simulation will reduce the number of total possible simulations for baseline. Further selection will be done depending on the simulations to be carried out in WP3, so the most promising categories and duty cycles would be selected for adding ESS or implement driving and energy management strategies.

The specific example of the conventional tram of Figure 4 will be used for validation of OPEUS tool, before introducing the ESS. This validation is included in

WP02. Additional validations will be done with FINE1 partners (DB and SNCF) for the regional and high speed profiles.

4.2 Auxiliary operations

In Task 05.2 (future task) a sensitivity analysis for the effect of auxiliary and operational aspects will be investigated by simulating variations from a chosen and representative system architecture and duty cycle (e.g. conventional tram) using OPEUS tool. To show the results, the energy consumption will be compared evaluating the effect of an auxiliary load occurring during the different operational phases of the duty cycle (acceleration, steady state, braking and parking).

In the current work of Task 05.1 the auxiliary system is described and defined (as already mentioned earlier the auxiliary description and values used for the simulation in OPEUS for every service category are included in Annex A of Deliverable 02.1 OPEUS simulation methodology).

The auxiliary load is implemented during different periods of the duty cycle. Figure 5 shows the four parts a duty cycle can be divided into: acceleration, constant velocity, coasting and braking.

Figure 5: Phases of a vehicle speed profile

- Phase I: Acceleration until desired speed is reached
- Phase II: Cruising with a constant velocity for a defined time period

- Phase III: Coasting until the remaining distance is equal to the required braking way
- Phase IV: Braking until the train stops

In order to assess the influence of the auxiliary consumption different strategies can be implemented. The normal of basic case has a constant auxiliary load over the entire cycle. In the worst case, all the load applies during the acceleration phase, while for the best case the load only occurs during the braking process.

For comparison reasons the total amount of auxiliary energy consumed is kept the same for all cases, which means that not only the time but also the total amount of power will be varied in the different proposed scenarios.

Table 4 is proposed as the results to be obtained in task 05.2 to make the analysis on auxiliary consumption, studying the effect of having an ESS (based on a battery) or not having an ESS.

Scenario	Case	Energy Consumption	
		Conventional Tram	Tram with battery as ESS
AUX in braking phases	Best		
AUX in non-traction phases (coast, brake)			
Constant AUX	Basic		
AUX in traction phases (acceleration, constant drive)			
AUX in acceleration phases	Worst		

Table 4 Result template for auxiliary operation simulation

The best and worst cases are only theoretic scenarios and will be simulated to show the effect on energy consumption. However these scenarios give a hint on the positive effect a system with an ESS could have. The ESS could store the available energy during the braking process and release it over time to feed the auxiliary load. This effect can only be used when the maximum amount of energy storable in the ESS is sufficient and will be investigated in task 05.2.

Additional boundary conditions are:

- Trajectory: tram
- In both, conventional tram and tram with ESS, the auxiliaries are supplied by braking energy during braking phases;
- At stops the auxiliary power is supplied by the auxiliary converter in both conventional tram and tram with ESS.

Other proposal strategies

To investigate possible measures for reduction of energy losses in task 05.2 energy management strategy proposals shall be made. A first list of proposals is presented in this deliverable, which will be agreed within OPEUS working group and extended or changed after first simulations in WP03.

- **Optimum operation:** as the efficiency maps of all the traction components were defined together with FINE1 partners it is possible to extract optimum operation points for every component. This strategy means to develop a control operating strategy to drive in the best operating points for the whole traction system.
- **Switching off one (or more) traction motors:** in low load requirements this control strategy can be very efficient, as traction motors are more efficient when working at high loads. Therefore, it should be avoided balancing a low load among all traction motors, but to use the minimum number of motor at best efficiency point. However, even though a traction motor is switched off, its auxiliaries may still run. The influence of such strategy in auxiliaries and energy consumption will be assessed.
- **Other parameters** to be changed and investigated in order to check the influence in energy consumption and that are not related to operation strategies, but to design, can be:
 - Total mass of the train: the mass of a train has a significant impact on the energy consumption because a higher mass also leads to a reduced acceleration performance. This means that for a given timetable and vehicle, a lightweight train reaches the set speed of the track faster and spends therefore a higher amount of time with constant speeds or coasting, which in return leads to a reduced energy consumption. In addition the mass of the train influences

directly the weight related driving resistance of the vehicle (factor k_2 in resistance formula, as defined in the in Annex A of Deliverable 02.1 OPEUS simulation methodology.

- Running resistance: the resistance factor k_4 is responsible for the calculation of the aerodynamic drag of the train vehicle. The force acting on the vehicle is obtained by multiplying the factor k_4 with the square of the current vehicle speed in m/s. In general, all vehicles (e.g. rail, road...) benefit from improved aerodynamics in terms of energy consumption. It may be interesting to check the influence in urban and in high speed vehicles.

5 CONCLUSION

This report describes the traction system and auxiliary parameter based on the vehicle architecture related to the different scenarios.

The topologies presented are general, and include dotted lines for alternative component or interface variants, so OPEUS simulation tool will provide the user with the option to choose a specific variant to be simulated.

A specific conventional tram architecture is presented as example, where all traction components (converters, traction motors, etc.) are defined and described.

A first proposal of topologies as well as some energy and management strategies to run simulations with OPEUS Tool and to investigate possible measures for reduction of energy losses in task 5.2 of WP5 is made. This proposal can be updated depending on the simulations results that will be obtained in WP3 and WP5, as the objective is that after simulations the most promising categories and duty cycles are selected for adding ESS or implement driving and energy management strategies. The final proposal will be reviewed in OPEUS working group.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] L. Pröhl, „OPEUS Deliverable - DO2.1 OPEUS simulation methodology,“ EU-project OPEUS, Rostock, 2017.

